

THE CONSTITUTION OF SWIETENINE, THE NON-BITTER PRINCIPLE OF THE SEEDS OF *SWIETENIA MACROPHYLLA* KING. PART II

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Swietenine, $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$, the non-bitter lactonic principle of *Swietenia macrophylla*, upon dehydrogenation with selenium at 300° in a sealed tube produces a hydrocarbon, swieten, $C_{16}H_{20}$. It has been characterised as a polyalkylnaphthalene from its U. V. spectrum and other pertinent physical and chemical data. This observation, coupled with chemical and spectral evidences, indicates a hydro-naphthalene lactone structure for swietenine.

Swietenine, the non-bitter, lactonic principle of *Swietenia macrophylla* King (N. O. *Meliaceae*) was reported earlier to have the partial structure (I) by the present authors (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 179).

Further elucidation of its constitution has been possible from a study of the nature of its selenium dehydrogenation products. A discussion on this subject and relevant data are presented here. Dehydrogenation experiments were carried out with swietenine both in sealed and open tubes.

With black selenium at 300° in a sealed tube, swietenine smoothly decomposed giving rise to a mixture of several compounds from which a liquid hydrocarbon (b. p. $129^\circ/0.03$ mm) was obtained as the principal constituent. This compound has been designated

as swieten, $C_{16}H_{20}$, although the possibility of its having $C_{17}H_{22}$ formula cannot be excluded simply from C-H analyses. This point can only be clarified by the synthesis of swieten, which is under way. The hydrocarbon was rendered pure and homogeneous by repeated chromatography over Brockmann alumina (vide Experimental). It exhibits a bluish violet fluorescence in solution and readily forms an orange crystalline trinitrobenzolate which analyses for $C_{16}H_{20}.C_6H_3(NO_2)_3$. Swieten carries two methyl groups. Its ultraviolet spectrum (Fig. 1) (λ_{max} at $238 m\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 4.81 and at $283 m\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 3.72) resembles closely that of alkyl-naphthalenes and exhibits a bathochromic shift characteristics of polyalkylated naphthalene derivatives (Braude, *Ann. Reports*, 1945, 42, 105). From U. V. spectrum and extinction values

FIG. 1

swieten is thus proved to be a polyalkylated naphthalene. The possibility of its being a phenanthrene, anthracene or phenalan derivative has also been considered. The first two appear to be unlikely from a consideration of (a) their ultraviolet spectra (Braude, *loc. cit.*; Morton and De Gouveia, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 927; Askew, *ibid.*, 1935, 509; Cocker and Hayes, *ibid.*, 1951, 844; Mosby, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 76, 3848; Heilbronner, Fröklicher and Plattner, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1949, 32, 2479), (b) high percentage of hydrogen in swieten, and (c) ready oxidation of its -C.Me functions which is not to be expected if the methyl groups are directly attached to the anthracene and phenanthrene nucleus. A tetrahydrophenanthrene or tetrahydroanthracene expression for swieten (methyl groups in reduced rings) would not be unlikely. But they are readily transformed into the corresponding aromatic systems at 300° in presence of selenium, as experienced from model experiments. The phenalan constitution of swieten is also untenable although its U. V. spectrum (Buchi and Pappas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2963) is similar to that of naphthalene and swieten. The latter, unlike phenalan, fails to undergo (a) catalytic hydrogenation and (b) does not form keto-dicarboxylic acid on oxidation with potassium ferricyanide (Buchi and Pappas, *loc. cit.*). From a consideration of all available evidence, swieten could best be represented by polyalkylnaphthalene structure (II).

Now, swietenine, from which swieten (II) is derived, is not an aromatic compound. Therefore, the naphthalene moiety in (II) must have been formed from the corresponding hydronaphthalene system occurring in swietenine, and the most probable constitution of this substance thus appears as (III) :

The positions of the lactone ring and other functional groups are yet to be ascertained and further work in this line is in progress. But from the present knowledge of the chemistry of swietenine, it can be said that the lactone ring remains directly fused with the hydronaphthalene nucleus.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Selenium Dehydrogenation of Swietenine in a sealed tube.—An intimate mixture of swietenine (1.0 g.) and black pulverised selenium (1.0 g.) was heated in a sealed tube at 300° for 4 hours, and then at 310°-320° for 5 hours. After cooling, the tube was broken

and the brown mass was extracted with ether which was evaporated off. The gummy residue was taken up with petroleum ether (b. p. 40°-60°) and filtered through a column of Brockmann alumina. The filtrate on evaporation left a brown mass which on high vacuum sublimation at 120-50°/0.03 mm gave an orange coloured viscous oil (0.80 g.). This was dissolved in 30 c.c. of petroleum ether and the clear solution, thus obtained, was column-chromatographed over alumina (18 cm × 1 cm), using the same solvent as eluent. The eluate was collected in six fractions of 5 c.c. each. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Fractions.	Product on evaporation.	Yield.
1	Brown liquid	16 mg.
2	Orange, viscous liquid exhibiting blue fluorescence	29
3	Do	20
4	Do	9
5	Nil	...
6	Nil	...

Alcoholic solution of each of the residues from fractions 2, 3 and 4, on treatment with alcoholic trinitrobenzene, yielded identical silky orange crystalline trinitrobenzoate, m. p. 152.5-53° which showed no depression in their mixed melting points. [Found (in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ for 4 hours at 80°): C, 63.35; H, 5.61; N, 9.34; -C.Me, 7.16. C₁₆H₂₀.C₆H₃(NO₂)₃ requires C, 62.12; H, 5.41; N, 9.88; 2C.Me, 7.06%).

Regeneration of Swieten.—The trinitrobenzoate (0.1 g.) was decomposed chromatographically over activated alumina (50 mg.) using petroleum ether as the eluent. The pure and homogeneous swieten, isolated thereby, distilled at 120°/0.03 mm, yield 40 mg. It formed crystalline trinitrobenzoate, m. p. 152.5-153° which did not show depression when mixed with the trinitrobenzoates obtained before. The ultraviolet absorption spectrum of swieten (Fig. 1) shows the maximum at 238, 249, 254 and 283mμ, corresponding log *ε* values being 4.81, 4.62, 4.62 and 3.72 respectively. It failed to take up hydrogen when its alcoholic solution was subjected to catalytic hydrogenation in presence of Adams' catalyst. (Found in a dry sample: C, 89.92; H, 9.42; C.Me, 13.01. C₁₆H₂₀ requires C, 90.57; H, 9.43; 2 C.Me, 14.15%).

Fraction (1) (Table I) furnished a brown oily gum. It showed no tendency to crystallise but could be coupled with diazobenzene chloride to a red solid in alkaline solution. With alcoholic ferric chloride it developed a green coloration. A red intractable gummy product was obtained when this phenolic portion was treated with an alcoholic solution of trinitrobenzene.

Selenium Dehydrogenation of Swietenine in an open tube.—An intimate mixture of swietenine (0.5 g.) and selenium powder (0.5 g.) was heated in a metal-bath at 350° for 30 minutes. The dark brown mass was allowed to cool and the test tube with its contents was crushed with sea-sand and soxhletted with benzene for 16 hours. The

brown benzene extract having a green fluorescence was filtered and the filtrate on evaporation of the solvent left a brown gummy residue which on high vacuum distillation at 110-120°/0.01 mm, yielded an orange coloured viscous oil (30 mg.). It did neither crystallise nor produced crystalline picrate with alcoholic picric acid.

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